

Primordial High Energy Neutrinos

Theoretical & observational constraints and sharp
spectral features

Nicolas Grimbaum Yamamoto

arXiv:[2507.02063](https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.02063) in collaboration with T.Hambye

Summary •

1 • Motivations

2 • Sharp spectral features

3 • Medium interactions

4 • Constraints

Motivations.

→ **Primordial High
Energy Neutrinos
(PHENUs)**

Motivations.

→ Primordial High Energy Neutrinos (PHENUs)

Motivations.

→ Primordial High Energy Mewtrinos (PHEMEW) !

Motivations.

→ Primordial High Energy Mewtrinos (PHEMEW) !

Sharp Spectral Features.

Decays

Out of equilibrium annihilation

Medium interactions.

$$S_\nu(z_e, E_0) = \int_0^{z_e} \frac{dz}{(1+z)H(z)} \langle \sigma v \rangle n_{\nu_{BG}}$$

Medium interactions.

$$S_\nu(z_e, E_0) = \int_0^{z_e} \frac{dz}{(1+z)H(z)} \langle \sigma v \rangle n_{\nu_{BG}}$$

Average number
of scattering

Medium interactions.

$$S_\nu(z_e, E_0) = \int_0^{z_e} \frac{dz}{(1+z)H(z)} \langle \sigma v \rangle n_{\nu_{BG}}$$

Average number
of scattering

Integration
over the line of
sight

Medium interactions.

$$S_\nu(z_e, E_0) = \int_0^{z_e} \frac{dz}{(1+z)H(z)} \langle \sigma v \rangle n_{\nu_{BG}}$$

Average number of scattering
Integration over the line of sight
cross section averaged over target distribution function

Medium interactions.

$$S_\nu(z_e, E_0) = \int_0^{z_e} \frac{dz}{(1+z)H(z)} \langle \sigma v \rangle n_{\nu BG}$$

Average number of scattering
 Integration over the line of sight
 cross section averaged over target distribution function
 target neutrino number density

$$f = \frac{\Omega_P^0}{\Omega_{DM}^0}$$

Medium interactions.

Sharp spectral features mostly unaffected

Average number of scattering

Integration over the line of sight

Background neutrino number density

Thermally averaged cross section

$$E_\nu^{inj} = E_\nu^0(1+z)$$

$$t_{inj} = t(z)$$

$$f = \frac{\Omega_P^0}{\Omega_{DM}^0}$$

Constraints.

Vitagliano, Tamborra, Raffelt '19

Observational:

- Atmospheric flux (SuperKamiokande, Icecube) > 50 MeV
- Astrophysical flux (Icecube) < 5 PeV
- DSNB > 5 MeV (Soon)

Constraints.

Vitagliano, Tamborra, Raffelt '19

Observational:

- Atmospheric flux (SuperKamiokande, Icecube) > 50 MeV
- Astrophysical flux (Icecube) < 5 PeV
- DSNB > 5 MeV (Soon)

PHENU flux must be at most of the value of the observed flux

→ Upper bound on f

Constraints

Theoretical:

N_{eff} bound on additional neutrino energy density

Bianco, Depta, Frerick, Hambye, Hufnagel, Schmidt-Hoberg '25
 Hambye, Hufnagel, Lucca, '21
 Acharya, Khatri, '19

Constraints

Theoretical:

BBN bound from photo and hadro disintegration of light elements

N_{eff} bound on additional neutrino energy density

Bianco, Depta, Frerick, Hambye, Hufnagel, Schmidt-Hoberg '25
 Hambye, Hufnagel, Lucca, '21
 Acharya, Khatri, '19

Constraints.

Theoretical:

CMB anisotropies bound

BBN bound from photo and hadro disintegration of light elements

N_{eff} bound on additional neutrino energy density

Competing bounds
with observations

Bianco, Depta, Frerick, Hambye, Hufnagel, Schmidt-Hoberg '25
 Hambye, Hufnagel, Lucca, '21
 Acharya, Khatri, '19

Constraints.

Combination: $\frac{f^{th.}}{f^{obs.}}$

- Ratio > 1 : Unconstrained by theoretical bounds
- Ratio $> 10^{-2}$: Potentially **observable today**
- Ratio $< 10^{-2}$: Signal too weak to be observed
- Ratio $< 10^{-5}$: Hopeless

Constraints.

Combination: $\frac{f^{th.}}{f^{obs.}}$

- Ratio > 1: Unconstrained by theoretical bounds
- Ratio > 10⁻²: Potentially **observable today**
- Ratio < 10⁻²: Signal too weak to be observed
- Ratio < 10⁻⁵: Hopeless

$$10 \text{ TeV} \lesssim m_P \lesssim 10^{11} \text{ GeV} \quad 10^{-8} \lesssim f_P \lesssim 10^{-2}$$

$$10^9 \text{ s} \lesssim \tau_P \lesssim 10^{12.5} \text{ s}$$

Constraints.

Combination: $\frac{f^{th.}}{f^{obs.}}$

- Ratio > 1: Unconstrained by theoretical bounds
- Ratio > 10⁻²: Potentially observable today
- Ratio < 10⁻²: Signal too weak to be observed
- Ratio < 10⁻⁵: Hopeless

$$10 \text{ TeV} \lesssim m_P \lesssim 10^{11} \text{ GeV}$$

$$10^9 \text{ s} \lesssim \tau_P \lesssim 10^{12.5} \text{ s}$$

$$10^{-8} \lesssim f_P \lesssim 10^{-2}$$

Potentially observable in IceCube,
HyperK, KM3NeT

Bumps ?

PHENUs could potentially explain the KM3NeT event

Bumps ?

Substructure emerging in the diffuse astrophysical flux ~30 TeV and ~100 TeV

PHENUs could potentially explain the KM3NeT event

arXiv:2507.06002v1

Bumps ?

Substructure emerging in the diffuse astrophysical flux ~30 TeV and ~100 TeV

PHENUs could potentially explain the KM3NeT event

arXiv:2507.06002v1

Medium interactions II.

Medium interactions II.

Medium interactions II.

Stay tuned!

Take home message:

- PHENUs could be produced in the early universe with **sharp spectral features**
 - Scattering on the background or with other PHENUs is **negligible**
 - Sharp spectral features are **observable** for a range of lifetime, mass and abundance
-

Thank you for your **attention**

arXiv:2507.02063
26??.xxxx